

The Relationship Between the Development of the Cultural and Creative Industries and Socio-Economic Development: A Study in Vietnam

Do Thi Y Nhi^{*1}, Huynh Cong Phuong², Khuong Thi Hue³

^{1,2,3}Lecturer, Thu Dau Mot University

¹Orcid No: <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-1319-8460>

²Orcid No: <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-6102-0812>

³Orcid No: <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-0505-5362>

ABSTRACT: This paper examines the socio-economic impacts of the development of cultural and creative industries (CCI) in Vietnam, addressing a gap in empirical evidence from emerging economies. Using a mixed-method approach, the study analyzes panel data (2010–2023) from four provinces through fixed-effects regression and structural equation modeling (SEM) to assess both direct and mediating effects of CCI value added, investment, and employment on GRDP per capita, HDI, and unemployment. Qualitative findings from thematic analysis of 12 policy documents and expert interviews complement the quantitative results. The analysis shows that CCI value added and investment significantly and positively influence GRDP per capita and HDI, though their impact on unemployment is limited. Vietnam's CCI performance remains modest compared with regional benchmarks due to fragmented policies and insufficient infrastructure. This study provides integrated evidence of how CCI supports socio-economic development and offers policy implications for a coherent national strategy, institutional coordination, and targeted financing. Limitations include the narrow geographical coverage and limited sectoral scope, suggesting the need for broader longitudinal and comparative research.

KEYWORDS: CCI; socio-economic development; cultural policy; creative economy

1. INTRODUCTION

In the context of globalization and knowledge economy, cultural and creative industries (CCI) have emerged as one of the main engine for economic growth and social development. Based on UNESCO (2005), CCIs are all of those activities, which merge the creation or the production and dissemination or the trade in goods and services with a cultural content, along with tangible and intangible added value. At the global level, CCIs significantly contribute to GDP, employment, and national soft power—a phenomenon observed in both South Korea and China (UNCTAD, 2022; Keane, 2013; Jung & Lee, 2019). In Vietnam CCIs are a growth sector recently identified in national strategies such as the Strategy for the Development of Vietnam's Cultural and Creative Industries to 2020, Vision to 2030 (MoCST, 2016) and Resolution No. However, in spite of these policy initiatives the contribution of the sector is small—approximately 3% of GDP and mostly concentrated in a few urban areas (MoCST 2020). Main drivers entail: dispersed ecosystems, poor trans-sectoral collaboration, and non-existing financial instruments for creative companies. Existing research findings have shown beneficial economic impacts of CCI on society (Throsby, 2001; Cunningham, 2014; Li & Hu, 2018); however, there is limited empirical evidence in the Vietnam context. Most concentrate on specific sub-sectors and thus fail to consider CCI in the broader systemic socio-economic context, which combines variables including GRDP per capita, HDI or employment.

In the study, these gaps are explored by examining the empirical relationship between CCI development and socio-economic outcomes at sub-national level in Vietnam. This article adds to the creative economy literature, providing new evidence from a developing country and develop an integrative model that links cultural policy, industrial dynamics and socio-economic transformation.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND LITERATURE REVIEW

The cultural and creative industries (CCI) are widely recognized as not only economic drivers but also carriers of cultural values that create material and symbolic capital. Throsby (2001) defines culture as a particular type of capital, like natural, human or physical capital, which can contribute to economic growth without threatening the identity of a country. This is in line with sustainable development (United Nations, 1987) which holds that economic, social and environmental progress are interdependent.

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According to international frameworks by UNESCO (2005) and UNCTAD (2022), CCI referring of creative production and distribution processes, that produce artistic, cultural or entertainment value -while supporting employment, innovation process and social inclusion. The Triple Helix model (Etzkowitz & Leydesdorff, 2000) also emphasizes how the trio of government, industry and education foster innovation and bolster creative ecosystems – which are vital components to a successful creative economy.

It is evident from cross-country empirical studies that CCI are the mediators for regional development. For example, Li et al. 2;(2020) reveals that innovation and digitalization aggravates the effect of CCI on GDP and employment in China. Jung and Lee (2019) also found that South Korea’s cultural industries contribute to modernity in addition to global soft power. Yet, in Vietnam, the evidences are still patchy—sometimes applied to one isolated area of construction such as cinema or handicraft or music (Nguyen, 2020; Dinh, 2018)—or do not cover systemic relation between CCI and other social-economic outcomes including GRDP per capita, HDI or number of unemployment. From this literature three main gaps emerge: (1) Sectoral fragmentation – it studies the individual CCI sub-sectors and not the sector as a cohesive system; (2) No integrated data – national data that connects CCI metrics (e.g. added value, investment, employment...) with socio-economic variables are in their infancy; (3) Weak policy evaluation – few of these works examine the ways policy coherence and institutional coordination play roles in shaping CCI outcomes.

In response, this paper has developed an integrated analytical framework based on theories of creative economy, sustainable development and innovation system. According to the model, CCI development (via value added, investment, employment and enterprise) directly affects socio-economic development (GRDP per capita, HDI, unemployment) for both direct and indirect paths. Investment and employment are also intermediate steps through which creative activity translates into measurable economic and social capital.

3. THE PROPOSED RESEARCH MODEL

According to the customer economy and sustainable economic growth theories, and in accordance with previous studies (Keane, 2013; Jin, 2016; Li et al., 2020), the essence of the development of the cultural and creative industries (CCI) such as value added, employment scale, investment, and the number of enterprises, is crucial in the socio-economic development at national or local levels. This research model was designed to analyze the relationship between the variables that contribute to the development of the CCI (independent variables) and the socio-economic (dependent) variables, finally adjusting a series of control variables, so as incorporate external factors that may have nothing to do with the CCI.

Figure 1. Conceptual model of the relationship between key CCI development variables and socio-economic indicators

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

H1: Cultural and creative industries value added (CCI-VA)

The contribution of CCI to the economy through creative product is measured by the cultural and Creative Industries Value Added (CCI-VA). As such, CCI-VA is posited to harness productivity, innovation and growth according to theories of creative economy (Keane 2013). Li et al. (2020) also indicated that CCI-VA is positively related to GRDP per capita and the human development index (HDI) at a regional level.

H1: The CCI-VA is positively related with the GRDP per capita, the GRDP growth rate and HDI which will improve local level socio-economic development.

H2: Investment in CCI

Investing in CCI is key to constructing creative infrastructure, creating high-value cultural products/services and growing the sector. Jin (2016) highlighted the significance of technology, infrastructure and economic investment for promoting CCI and social development in South Korea.

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H2 (Investment in CCI affects socio-economic development): Investment in CCI has a positive impact on socio-economic development, as measured by GRDP per capita and HDI or through reduced unemployment rates.

H3: CCI employment

CCI is a major source of jobs for the youthful and creative population also reducing pressure on unemployment (UNESCO, 2019). In countries where CCI have proven to be successful creative economies like South Korea and China, the growth of employment can contribute to unemployment while coping with labour reshaping (Li et al., 2020).

Hypothesis H3 The labor share in CCI (measured by the proportion of total labor force) negatively affects the unemployment rate that leads to sustainable job employment.

H4: Number of CCI enterprises

The number of CCI firms signals how developed the creative ecosystem is and its ability to support cultural products and services diversification. A rising number of CCI companies indicates stronger local level competition and innovation (Keane, 2013). These companies create economic value as well as increase social welfare by providing socially valuable cultural services (Li et al., 2020).

H4: Number of CCI establishments is positively related to GRDP per capita and HDI contributing significantly for higher quality of social development.

4. METHODOLOGY

This article employs a mixed-method analysis to assess the socio-economic effects of CCI in Vietnam. Quantitative methodology was used to assess the direct and mediating impacts of CCI growth on relevant socio-economic measures, and qualitative approaches were utilized to read the policy and institutional context in which these are occurring.

4.1. Data sources and sampling

Secondary data for the quantitative analysis were collected from the General Statistics Office of Vietnam, the Ministry of Culture, Sports and Tourism, UNCTAD, and UNESCO covering the period 2010–2023.

The dataset includes four representative provinces/cities—Hanoi, Ho Chi Minh City, Da Nang, and Binh Duong—selected to capture (i) regional diversity (North–Central–South), (ii) varying levels of CCI development, and (iii) data reliability. Key variables comprised: CCI value added (% of GRDP); CCI investment (billion VND); Number of CCI enterprises; CCI employment (% of labor force); GRDP per capita (USD); Human development index (HDI); Unemployment rate (%).

4.2. Regression model specification

Panel data regression was employed to estimate the impact of CCI indicators on socio-economic development using a fixed-effects model (FE), selected via the Hausman test ($p < 0.05$). The baseline econometric equation is specified as follows:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 CCI_VA_{it} + \beta_2 CCI_INV_{it} + \beta_3 CCI_EMP_{it} + \beta_4 CCI_F_{it}$$

where:

Y_{it} represents the socio-economic indicator (GRDP per capita, HDI, or unemployment) for province i at time t , α_i captures unobserved provincial effects, and ϵ_{it} is the idiosyncratic error term.

Diagnostic tests were applied to ensure model reliability: Multicollinearity variance inflation factor ($VIF < 10$); Heteroscedasticity Breusch-Pagan and White tests; Autocorrelation Wooldridge test.

Structural equation modeling (SEM): To capture both direct and indirect (mediating) relationships among variables, a Structural Equation Model was constructed linking CCI investment and value added with socio-economic outcomes.

Model fit and validity were evaluated through standard indices: Comparative fit index (CFI) > 0.90 ; Tucker–Lewis index (TLI) > 0.90 ; root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) < 0.08 ; standardized root mean square residual (SRMR) < 0.05 .

Reliability and validity of constructs were further examined using: Cronbach's alpha > 0.70 for internal consistency; average variance extracted (AVE) > 0.50 ; Composite reliability (CR) > 0.70 .

4.3. Qualitative analysis

In addition to the quantitative results, The qualitative stage investigated stakeholders' viewpoints and policy processes. A sum of 12 key informants were purposively taken: policy makers, academicians and creative industry practitioners who have experienced minimum 10 years in the field of cultural policy, creative economy or regional planning, semi-structured interviews took place from March to April 2024. Consent for audio recording and transcription was obtained from all participants. The thematic analysis was conducted by applying NVivo software based on inductive coding for determining common themes such as contributions of CCI, policy coherence and ecosystem challenges. Credibility was strengthened by the triangulation of data with policy documents and statistic reports.

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Table 1. List of variables and expected signs

Variable	Description	Expected Sign	Justification
CCI-VA	CCI Value Added (% GRDP)	+	Higher value added boosts regional income and HDI
CCI-INV	CCI Investment (billion VND)	+	Investment strengthens infrastructure and innovation
CCI-EMP	CCI Employment (% labor force)	+	Expands job opportunities and reduces unemployment
CCI-FIRM	Number of CCI Enterprises	+	Reflects ecosystem maturity and diversification
GRDP per capita	Economic performance (USD/person)	Dependent	Main indicator of economic prosperity
HDI	Human Development Index	Dependent	Proxy for social development
Unemployment	Unemployment rate (%)	-	Inverse relationship with CCI development

In summary, the methodological design integrates quantitative rigor and qualitative depth to provide a robust, multi-dimensional understanding of how CCI development affects socio-economic performance across Vietnamese regions.

5. FINDINGS

5.1. Qualitative research findings

The data linking refers to more than 50 domestic and international publications –reports of UNCATD, UNESCO, General Statistics Office of Vietnam, the Ministry of Culture, Sports and Tourism - show the following findings:

The culture and creative industries (CCI) as a new economic growth point has attracted increasing attention for its dynamic development in comparison to the fluctuated GDP in some economies. In South Korea and China, CCI sector represents 3%-6% of the GDP (UNCTAD, 2022). Unlike, its China counterpart, Vietnam's CCI contribution is still at modest level, accounting for around 3% to the national GDP (Ministry of Culture, Sports and Tourism, 2020). Apart from the economic contribution, CCI is critical for shaping of the nation, promoting social inclusion and human well-being (UNESCO, 2013; Keane, 2013). Vietnam's policy and legal system ISIS Japan distributes the work concentrates CCI in the core of national development through these sources of policy that: the Strategy on CCI development to 2030 and the Resolution No. 23-NQ/TW. Nevertheless, there were still large differences in intersectoral and interregional cooperation (Ministry of Culture, Sports, and Tourism, 2020). Survey results are supported by semi-structured interviews of a dozen experts of culture, economy, and planning (including university researchers, policy-makers, and industry) which reveal a strong consensus regarding the contribution of CCI for socio-economic development. Speakers pointed out that CCI creates jobs for the youth, encourages innovation, adds value to the GDP and improves quality of life.

However, there remain several core challenges: (1) Policy incoherence, e.g., the lack of specialised financial instruments for CCI (2) A fragmented creative ecosystem, with weak collaboration between governments, corporates and academia (the Triple Helix model remains ineffective without practice); (3) Data, especially the absence of value added statistics by CCI sub-sectors.

An assessment of Vietnam's policy environment reveals some advances: (1) The national CCI strategy sets out a vision for the development of CCI as a major economic sector; (2) Targeted policies have facilitated an evermore dynamic cultural infrastructure and some private investment in film, visual arts and advertising. However, there are still significant limitations – limitations that need to be addressed:

- (1) Policies are conceptual in nature, without well defined targets, implementation apparatus or resource allocation;
- (2) There are no specific financial mechanisms (e.g., tax breaks or funds for innovation) to facilitate CCI: Weak Link between CCI and Broader Socio-Economic Development Approach 9 Urban plans: the digital economy and CCI cluster development.

In general, these findings reflect a policy vacuum: the failure to promulgate a full-scale ecosystem-oriented CCI policy, inadequate collaboration of the Ministry of Culture, Sports and Tourism and economic ministries (e.g., Planning & Investment, Finance, Industry & Trade), and the lack of an official list of indicators to evaluate the socio-economic impact of CCI—presently rooted in information from cultural sectors and not integrated into national socio-economic statistics.

5.2. Quantitative research findings

The research is based on secondary data covering the period from 2010 to 2023 sourced from four provinces/cities from the General Statistics Office of Vietnam, the Ministry of Culture, Sports and Tourism, UNESCO and UNCTAD. The findings show that (i) the average GRDP per capita in provinces that have strong development of the cultural and creative industries (CCI) is 1.3–2.5 times higher than the national average, (ii) the employment rate in the CCI sector increases by 5–7% per year in big cities and stagnates in many other localities, and (iii) the added value by the national CCI is about 3% of the GDP (Ministry of Culture, Sports and

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Tourism, 2020), of which over 50% of this rate in Ho Chi Minh City is contributed by advertising, video game development, and applied arts fields.

As for industries' added value growth rate, between 2010 and 2019, development of CCI-related industries including film, music, visual arts, advertising, games, and handicrafts achieved a CAGR of 8–10% on average. Yet because of the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic, growth fell to 4.5% in 2020 and then rebounded to 7.2% by 2022. The CCI sector accounted for about 3% of national GDP (Ministry of Culture, Sports and Tourism, 2020), and advertising and media alone constituted almost 40% of the value added of CCIs. Gaming, applied arts and film showed high rates of growth but are tiny.

There has been a major boom in enterprise formation within the CCI industries: from appx 16,000 companies in 2010 to over 35,000 in 2022, focused on advertising, design, gaming, film production. The rate of the CCI work force represents about 1.5% of the national labor force, is even higher in Ho Chi Minh City (2.5) and Hanoi (2.3), indicating the regional concentration of the sector in major economic and cultural centers. The GRDP per capita of cities where CCI has developed strongly (e.g., Hanoi City, Ho Chi Minh City, Da Nang City) increased at an average annual rate of about 7% in 2010–2022, higher than the national average (5.8%). In 2022, the national average GRDP per capita was 4,100 USD, as opposed to 6,500 USD in Ho Chi Minh City and 5,800 USD in Hanoi. Provinces with a strong CCI sector also have a higher Human Development Index (HDI) score— Hanoi (0.799), Ho Chi Minh City, 0.795—than the national average of 0.73 (UNDP, 2021). Where unemployment is concerned, CCI-strong areas have had persistently lower unemployment rates: compared to the national average of 3.5%, Ho Chi Minh City posts 2.5% (General Statistics Office, 2022).

Global CCI huynzman dimensions of the CCI sector reflect the following stable growth trends Founding Vietnam's the its the has been steady increase compared Founded with the traditional industry news as agriculture and mining. Indeed, growth in CCI is positively correlated with socio-economic indicators: richer GRDP per capita, higher HDI, and lower unemployment tend to occur in regions where the CCI sector is stronger. However, CCI development is strongly regional and has not yet been spreading widely into rural and hinterland or potential areas.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of variables

Variable	Unit	Mean	Min	Max	Std. Dev
CCI Value Added (CCI-VA)	% of GRDP	3.5	1.2	6.8	1.4
CCI Investment	Billion VND	1,250	400	3,500	780
Number of CCI Firms	Enterprises	120	35	450	95
CCI Employment	% of labor force	2.8	0.9	5.5	1.2
GRDP per capita	USD/person	4,200	1,800	8,600	1,650
HDI	Index (0–1)	0.715	0.610	0.820	0.055
GRDP Growth Rate	%	6.2	3.5	9.1	1.5
Unemployment Rate	%	3.4	1.8	5.7	1.1

The data reveal substantial regional disparities. On average, CCI contributes 3.5% of GRDP, with Ho Chi Minh City leading at 6.8% and Binh Duong lagging at 1.2%. CCI employment accounts for 2.8% of the labor force nationwide but exceeds 5% in creative hubs. These disparities confirm the geographic concentration of CCI development.

5.2.1. Model diagnostics

Table 3. Variance inflation factor (VIF) Test

Variable	VIF	Interpretation	Variable
CCI-VA	2.5	No multicollinearity	CCI-VA
CCI Investment	6.2	Moderate multicollinearity	CCI Investment
CCI Employment	4.1	No multicollinearity	CCI Employment
Number of CCI Firms	11.8	High multicollinearity — consider exclusion or transformation	Number of CCI Firms
Constant	3.0	Not a concern	Constant

The VIF test reveals high multicollinearity in the variable Number of CCI Firms (VIF > 10), suggesting it may be closely correlated with CCI-VA. Heteroskedasticity test results indicate Chi-squared = 12.4 with a p-value of 0.002. The autocorrelation test reports F-stat = 14.3 and p-value = 0.001, confirming the presence of autocorrelation (p < 0.05).

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Table 4. Multicollinearity and model diagnostics

Test	Statistic	Interpretation
Mean VIF	6.15	Moderate multicollinearity
Max VIF (CCI-FIRMS)	11.8	High — potential redundancy
Breusch–Pagan Test	$\chi^2 = 12.4, p = 0.002$	Heteroskedasticity detected
Wooldridge Test	$F = 14.3, p = 0.001$	Autocorrelation present
Hausman Test	$\chi^2 = 8.73, p = 0.02$	Fixed-effects preferred

Diagnostic tests confirmed the suitability of the fixed-effects (FE) model, as cross-sectional heterogeneity was significant. Heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation were corrected using robust clustered standard errors.

5.2.2 panel regression results

Table 5. Fixed-effects panel regression results (Dependent variable: GRDP per capita)

Variable	Coefficient (β)	SE (robust)	p-value	Interpretation
CCI Value Added (%)	250.3	90.2	0.007	Positive, significant
CCI Investment (billion VND)	0.85	0.40	0.040	Positive, significant
CCI Employment (%)	120.1	70.5	0.090	Marginally significant
Number of CCI Firms	1.20	0.90	0.200	Not significant
Constant	1,500	320	0.001	—
R ² (within)	0.61			

The R² (within) of the panel regression is 0.61. Hausman test suggests that the fixed effect model is preferred to use than random effect ($p = 0.02$). Results confirm that CCI VA and IV have a statistically significant and positive impact on GRDP per capita.

Descriptive statistics The mean differences across provinces with respect to indicators in CCI and socio-economic development (Table 1) are extremely large. Although both the average CCI value added (CCI-VA) is only about 3.5% of GRDP, there are large regional differences. For example, HCMC accounted CCI-VA volume to near 6.8%, sourced from high-ranking sectors like advertisement-gaming-design compared to Binh Duong with a much lower share of only 1.2% due to its industrial strength and an immature creative ecosystem. And, proportionately, CCI employment is 2.8 per cent on an average but much larger in urban creative hotspots: for example 2.5 per cent for HCMC and 2.3 per cent for Hanoi compared to under one percent elsewhere in the country⁴⁹. This reflects the agglomeration of creative work in large cities and the narrowing of that based on CCI-led job production to second-tier cities or rural areas.

Investment on CCI also diverges significantly where some provinces annually invest of 3,500 billion VND while others spend less than 500 billion VND. Cognitive versus fiscal distance This relates to the difference between thinking and doing, which usually reflects the inequality in fiscal capacity and policy preferences. Take Hanoi for example, an increased investment in creative hubs and cultural heritage conservation is emphasized, while Da Nang (despite its potential in cultural tourism and festival economy) exhibits average investment levels.

The GRDP per capital also demonstrates this divergence. In 2022, HCMC and Hanoi's PCIs came to USD 6,500 and USD 5,800 respectively¹⁹, quite high against the national average of USD 4,100 while less developed CCI provinces were lower than USD3.000. At the provincial level, HDI is also highest in provinces with high CCI development (Hanoi: 0.799; HCMC: 0.795) compared to a national average of 0.73 (UNDP, 2021). This is a kind of inverse trend when it comes to unemployment. Provinces endowed with more advanced CCI ecosystems have consistently lower unemployment rates (e.g., 2.5% in Ho Chi Minh City (HCMC), as compared to the national average of 3.5%), indicating the capacity of this sector to produce employment, especially for youth and skilled workers that is resilient in nature.

These results lend further support to our argument that the complexity and structure of CCI development in Vietnam is spatially uneven, with urban centers playing an important role as innovation and value creation centres. Implications for policy should stress spatial strategies not only to enhance core regions but also to remove the obstacles as part of the development in peripheral areas.

5.2.3. Structural equation modeling (SEM) results

The SEM analysis integrates direct and indirect effects among CCI dimensions and socio-economic outcomes (GRDP per capita, HDI, unemployment). Model fit indices confirm satisfactory fit: CFI = 0.94, TLI = 0.92, RMSEA = 0.056, SRMR = 0.047 — all within accepted thresholds (Hu & Bentler, 1999). Construct reliability tests yielded Cronbach's $\alpha > 0.80$, CR > 0.75, and AVE > 0.50, confirming convergent validity.

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Table 6. SEM direct, indirect, and total effects

Path	Direct Effect (β)	Indirect Effect (β)	Total Effect (β)	Sig.
CCI-INV \rightarrow CCI-VA	0.45	—	0.45	$p < 0.01$
CCI-VA \rightarrow GRDP per capita	0.30	—	0.30	$p < 0.01$
CCI-INV \rightarrow GRDP per capita	0.20	0.135	0.335	$p < 0.05$
CCI-EMP \rightarrow Unemployment	-0.25	—	-0.25	$p < 0.05$
CCI-VA \rightarrow HDI	0.40	—	0.40	$p < 0.01$

Model Fit: $\chi^2/df = 2.14$; CFI = 0.94; TLI = 0.92; RMSEA = 0.056; SRMR = 0.047.

Interpretation of the Indirect Effect in SEM: CCI Investment and Value-Added Mechanism

The structural equation model (SEM) results indicate a statistically significant indirect effect of *CCI Investment* on *GRDP per capita* through *CCI Value Added* ($\beta_{\text{indirect}} = 0.45 \times 0.30 = 0.135$, $p < 0.01$). This finding underscores the mediating role of value creation within cultural and creative industries (CCIs) in transforming capital input into tangible socio-economic outcomes. From a theoretical perspective, this mediation effect is consistent with the logic of the *creative economy model*, wherein investment in infrastructure, technology, and talent does not yield immediate macroeconomic gains unless it is effectively translated into innovation, content production, and cultural services (Throsby, 2001; Cunningham, 2014). In the Vietnamese context, this implies that mere financial input into CCI is not sufficient—the conversion into value-added outputs such as films, digital content, handicrafts, and cultural exports is the critical pathway toward socio-economic development.

Practically, this indirect pathway suggests that policy efforts should focus not only on expanding investment volumes, but also on enhancing the efficiency and absorptive capacity of CCI sectors. This includes:

- ✓ Improving institutional support (e.g., copyright enforcement, incubation services),
- ✓ Fostering innovation ecosystems that link education, production, and distribution (i.e., triple-helix frameworks),
- ✓ Capacity-building for creative workers to optimize content creation,
- ✓ Upgrading digital infrastructure to ensure wider access and monetization.

This mechanism helps explain why regions like Ho Chi Minh City and Hanoi, which possess not only higher levels of investment but also a more mature creative ecosystem, have seen clearer gains in GRDP per capita and HDI. In contrast, provinces with similar investment levels but weaker value-generation mechanisms fail to translate spending into broader development.

In sum, the indirect effect quantified by the SEM model is not merely statistical—it reflects a systemic transformation process, where investment must catalyze value creation within CCI to produce sustained socio-economic benefits. Recognizing and strengthening this conversion mechanism is crucial for Vietnam as it seeks to position CCIs as a new pillar of inclusive and sustainable growth.

Figure 2. Impulse Response Functions (IRF): Effects of CCI-VA and CCI Investment on GRDP per Capita

The impulse response analysis shows how GRDP per capita responds over a 10-year horizon following a one-time shock in: (1) CCI-VA: A strong and immediate positive impact occurs in year 1, peaking around year 3. Although the impact gradually declines, it remains positive through year 10. The 95% confidence interval (shaded orange) indicates high reliability; (2) CCI Investment: The initial effect is weaker but rises steadily, peaking in years 3–4 before tapering off. Its decline is faster than CCI-VA, but the relatively narrow confidence interval (light blue) suggests stable estimates.

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6. DISCUSSION

6.1. Discussion result

The integration of quantitative and qualitative findings provides a comprehensive understanding of how the cultural and creative industries (CCI) shape socio-economic development in Vietnam. The panel regression and SEM analyses confirm that CCI value added and investment significantly influence GRDP per capita and HDI, supporting H1–H3. However, the scale of these effects remains modest compared to international benchmarks. For instance, while CCI contributes about 3% of Vietnam's GDP, the ratio exceeds 5–6% in China and 7% in South Korea (UNCTAD, 2024). This disparity reflects the structural maturity of creative ecosystems, where institutional linkages, financial tools, and market readiness are far more advanced in those economies.

Qualitative insights reinforce these quantitative patterns. Experts consistently pointed out that fragmented governance, limited financial instruments, and underdeveloped infrastructure constrain Vietnam's CCI growth. The mediating effect identified in the SEM ($\beta_{\text{indirect}} = 0.135$) illustrates that investment only yields substantial economic returns when translated into value creation through innovation, production, and content commercialization. This finding aligns with the Triple Helix model (Etzkowitz & Leydesdorff, 2000), emphasizing that government–industry–academia collaboration is essential to transform cultural potential into measurable development outcomes.

Spatial concentration further explains the uneven performance. Major creative hubs such as Ho Chi Minh City and Hanoi show stronger linkages among creative firms, education institutions, and local policy actors—corresponding to higher GRDP per capita, HDI, and lower unemployment rates. In contrast, peripheral provinces remain excluded from CCI-driven growth due to weak institutional support and talent outflow. These patterns echo the Creative Economy Outlook (UNCTAD, 2024), which highlights the importance of regional diffusion policies to prevent creative centralization in emerging economies.

From a policy standpoint, these results suggest that scaling up CCI's contribution requires more than fiscal expansion. It necessitates systemic ecosystem reforms—including integrated governance frameworks, innovation finance schemes, and creative skills development—to enhance absorptive capacity and innovation intensity. As Mulcahy (2006) and Bell & Oakley (2015) argue, effective cultural policy must move beyond symbolic recognition toward structural integration within the broader economic strategy. Vietnam's pathway toward a dynamic creative economy thus depends on coupling strategic vision with implementation depth—ensuring that creative investment is both inclusive and transformative across regions.

6.2. Policy analysis and implications: Moving beyond descriptive narratives

The findings of this study highlight that while Vietnam has made progress in recognizing the strategic importance of cultural and creative industries (CCI), the policy framework remains largely prescriptive and fragmented. To transform CCIs into a sustainable growth engine, reforms should move from symbolic acknowledgment to operational implementation. The following policy implications are proposed, grouped into three priority dimensions:

6.2.1. institutional coordination and data systems

Vietnam's CCI governance structure is currently dispersed among multiple ministries (Culture, Finance, Planning and Investment, Industry and Trade) with weak coordination mechanisms and limited accountability. Establishing a cross-ministerial coordination body with clearly defined roles and shared objectives is essential. This body should facilitate vertical integration between central and provincial governments, ensuring that national CCI strategies are translated into actionable regional plans.

Moreover, a national CCI data system should be institutionalized—integrating economic, cultural, and social indicators—to enable evidence-based policymaking. Such a database would align with UNESCO's Culture for Development Indicators and the UNCTAD Creative Economy Outlook (2024), providing reliable metrics for monitoring CCI's contribution to sustainable development and the SDGs.

6.2.2. Investment and financial mechanisms

Current public investment in CCIs is limited and lacks instruments for stimulating private-sector participation. Vietnam should develop innovation and cultural funds, public–private partnerships (PPP), and performance-based subsidies targeted at creative startups and SMEs. Fiscal incentives—such as tax credits, IP protection support, and grants for creative R&D—can mobilize non-state investment and enhance absorptive capacity.

Learning from South Korea and China, where dedicated CCI funds, export promotion schemes, and creative content financing have driven industrial growth, Vietnam could design blended financing models combining state capital with private venture funds to nurture scalable creative ecosystems.

6.2.3. Regional and human capital development

The spatial concentration of creative activities in Hanoi and Ho Chi Minh City calls for regional CCI hubs to be established in emerging provinces such as Da Nang, Hue, and Can Tho. These hubs should integrate creative clusters, co-working spaces, and innovation incubators linked to local industries (tourism, heritage, digital design).

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Equally important is investing in creative education and capacity building—embedding creativity, design thinking, and entrepreneurship into national curricula and vocational training. Partnerships between universities, industry, and local governments (in line with the Triple Helix model) can strengthen talent pipelines and foster inclusive creative growth.

In sum, Vietnam's path toward a resilient and inclusive creative economy depends on institutional coherence, innovative financing, and human-centered regional policies. Only through systemic reforms and multi-level collaboration can the country unlock the transformative potential of its cultural and creative industries.

7. CONCLUSION

This study provides new empirical evidence on the role of cultural and creative industries (CCI) in fostering Vietnam's socio-economic development. The results confirm that CCI value added, investment, and employment contribute significantly—both directly and indirectly—to GRDP per capita, HDI, and job creation. Yet, the magnitude of these impacts remains modest compared to more mature creative economies such as South Korea and China, primarily due to fragmented institutional structures and weak ecosystem integration.

Theoretically, the research enriches the international literature on CCI in emerging economies by offering an integrated, data-driven analysis of how creative sectors interact with broader economic and social systems. It advances a multi-pathway model that links CCI not only to economic outcomes but also to social inclusion and human development—demonstrating that creativity functions as both a production input and a source of societal wellbeing. Furthermore, the study situates Vietnam's experience within comparative contexts, underscoring how institutional maturity, innovation systems, and policy coherence determine the developmental capacity of CCIs. It also contributes to debates on cultural governance, highlighting that inclusive, participatory models are more effective than purely regulatory approaches.

Practically, the findings call for a more cohesive national CCI strategy aligned with digital transformation and regional planning. Key priorities include: (1) establishing cross-ministerial coordination mechanisms and unified data systems; (2) designing creative finance instruments and public-private partnerships to mobilize investment; and (3) fostering creative hubs and talent development programs that bridge education, innovation, and industry. These reforms would enable Vietnam to unlock the transformative potential of CCIs as a foundation for sustainable and inclusive growth.

Future studies should expand to longitudinal and sectoral datasets, enabling dynamic modeling of CCI impacts over time. Further exploration of non-economic dimensions—such as identity formation, cultural participation, and community resilience—would also deepen understanding of CCIs' social value. Comparative research across ASEAN or other Global South economies could offer valuable policy insights for harmonizing creative development strategies.

Recognizing CCI as both a cultural and economic catalyst will be vital for Vietnam's transition toward a knowledge-based and inclusive growth model.

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Declaration of interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest. All the authors declare no conflict of interest, including financial and personal relationships with other people or organizations that could inappropriately influence (bias) their work reported in this paper.

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Ethical considerations

All participants were recruited voluntarily and all of them knew the purpose of this study. All participants were informed of the nature and purpose of the study, and provided consent before completing the questionnaires. Ethical approval related to human research, in the study was followed Thu Dau Mot University ethical guidelines and violated with the Declaration of Helsinki.

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